

1 **Chilean berry *Ugni molinae* Turcz fruit and leaves: interesting source**
2 **of antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-tyrosinase compounds**

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17 **ABSTRACT**

18 The knowledge of the biological properties of fruits and leaves of murta (*Ugni molinae*
19 Turcz) has been owned by native Chilean culture. The present study investigated the
20 phenolic content, the antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-tyrosinase activities of different
21 murta fruit and leaves extracts to approach their uses on future food, pharmaceutical and
22 cosmetic applications. Extractions of murta fruit and leaves were carried out under water,
23 ethanol and ethanol 50%. Phenolic content of these extracts was measured through Folin
24 Ciocalteu test and the antioxidant power by four different antioxidant systems (ORAC,
25 FRAP, DPPH and TEAC assays) owing to elucidate the main mechanism of antioxidant
26 action depending on the chemical composition of the extracts. Some flavonoids, such as
27 rutin, isoquercitrin and quercitrin hydrate were identified and quantified through HPLC
28 analysis. Antimicrobial activity was determined measuring minimum inhibition
29 concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) values against
30 *Escherichia coli* and *Listeria monocytogenes*, and the effect of these extracts on *L.*
31 *monocytogenes* was confirmed by flow cytometry. Results indicated phenolic content and
32 chemical composition of murta fruit and leaf extracts were considerably higher than other
33 fruits and plants, showing promising perspectives as potential ingredients for the cosmetic
34 and food industries. Murta leaves presented higher antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-
35 tyrosinase properties if compared with murta fruit, principally the hydroalcoholic extract.

36

37 *Keywords:* murta, natural extract, polyphenols, antioxidant, antimicrobial, tyrosinase
38 inhibitor

39

40 **Chemical compounds studied in this article:** 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH)
41 (PubChem CID 74358); 2,2'-azinobis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonate) (ABTS)
42 (PubChem CID 90658258); gallic acid (PubChem CID 370); Trolox ((PubChem CID
43 40634); sodium carbonate (PubChem CID 10340), AAPH (2,2-Azobis (2-
44 methylpropionamide) dihydrochloride (PubChem CID 76344); ferric 2,4,6-tripyridyl-
45 s-triazine (TPTZ) (PubChem CID 77258); fluorescein (PubChem CID 16850); arbutin
46 (PubChem CID 440936); kojic acid (PubChem CID 3840).

47

48 **1. Introduction**

49

50 During last years, there is an increasing interest in plant-derived products due to an
51 increasing demand for: i) natural food additives/products by consumers; ii) chemical
52 diversity in screening programs; and iii) seeking pharmacological drugs from natural
53 products without toxicological effects. Scientific community studies have focused on
54 natural products from medicinal plants, either as pure compounds or as plant extracts, as
55 an alternative solution for these demands due to their chemical composition rich in
56 bioactive compounds (Rios & Recio, 2005, Sasidharan et al., 2011).

57 Composition and traditional folk medicine of berries suggest significant health
58 benefits, but few studies to date have investigated these potentials through chemical and
59 biological activities (Fredes, 2009; Junqueira et al., 2015; Schreckinger, Lotton, Lila, &
60 Gonzalez de Mejia, 2010). It has been also confirmed that berries have higher antioxidant
61 capacity than other fruits and vegetables due to their high content in polyphenols. Several
62 studies have also found the consumption of berries is effective in prevention and treatment
63 of some diseases (Erlund et al., 2008; Suwalsky et al., 2007). Murta, murtilla, or
64 scientifically called *Ugni molinae* Turcz, is an aromatic Myrthacea specie native growing
65 in the coast and pre-Andean mountains of South Chile. This wild perennial shrub is
66 widely used in folk medicine by indigenous people, including Mapuche, Puelche and
67 Pehuenche cultures, for the treatment of several ailments, such as diarrhea, ulcers, fever,
68 inflammations and migraines. The scientific interest by this native shrub has emerged
69 recently, and since then, the chemical composition of this plant, both fruit and leaves, and
70 new potential applications of their compounds have been studied (Hauser et al., 2014;
71 Jofré et al., 2016; Junqueira et al., 2015; Peña-Cerda., et al., 2017; Rubilar et al., 2011;
72 Suwalsky et al., 2007). In this work, different extractions of fruit and leaves were

73 performed in order to obtain the highest amount of bioactive compounds with antioxidant,
74 antimicrobial and anti-tyrosinase activities. The aim of this study was to present a relation
75 between these activities with their chemical composition depending their polarity and
76 affinity with extractive solvents. Antioxidant activities were measured through different
77 assays owing to understand mechanisms of action of their active compounds.
78 Antimicrobial activity of murta extracts have been previously studied by other authors
79 (Hauser et al. 2014; Junqueira et al., 2015; Shene et al., 2009), but their MIC and MBC
80 values against pathogen bacteria have never been reported. On the other hand, nowadays
81 there is also an increasing interest by cosmetic industry for the searching of natural
82 tyrosinase inhibitors in order to substitute synthetic compounds used on anti-pigmenting
83 and skin protectors. Tyrosinase is the key enzyme involved in both mammalian
84 melanogenesis and fruit or fungi enzymatic browning (Chang, 2009, Kim & Uyama,
85 2005). Anti-tyrosinase compounds may help combat wrinkles and other signs of
86 premature aging, and delay some vegetable food products darkening. The principal aim
87 of this work was not finding the complete list of compounds from murta fruit and leaves,
88 but obtaining relevant data related to their antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-tyrosinase
89 activities.

90 Earlier studies were already focused on identifying the chemical composition of murta
91 fruit and leaves extracts under different solvents (Junqueira et al., 2015; Jofré et al., 2016;
92 López et al., 2017; Peña-Cerda., et al., 2017). Thus, the objective of this work was to
93 analyze the antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-tyrosinase activities of murta fruit and
94 leaves owing to validate their properties and traditional uses through scientific data for a
95 proper application on functional food, nutraceutical and cosmetic products.

96

97 **2. Materials and Methods**

98

99 2.1. *Plant material and reagents*

100

101 *Ugni Molinae* fruit and leaves were collected from Yumbel in the VIII Region of
102 Biobío in Chile by the company “Agrícola Pallauquen E.I.R.L. (37°50’S, 72°35’W). The
103 collected materials were dried (at 35 °C) to a constant weight and ground in a coffee
104 grinder. 2,2’-azinobis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulphonate) (ABTS), Folin Ciocalteu
105 phenol reagent, 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), anhydrous sodium carbonate,
106 gallic acid, AAPH (2,2-Azobis (2-methylpropionamide) dihydrochloride, ferric 2,4,6-
107 tripyridyl-s-triazine (TPTZ), 6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid
108 (Trolox) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Santiago, Chile). Kojic acid, arbutin,
109 catechin hydrate, rutin, isoquercitrin, ellagic acid dihydrate and quercitrin hydrate were
110 purchased from Sigma Aldrich Quimica S.A. (Madrid, Spain).

111 Culture preparation: *Listeria monocytogenes* CECT 934 (ATCC 19114) and
112 *Escherichia coli* CECT 434 (ATCC 25922) were chosen due to their relevance in food-
113 borne illness. Strains were obtained from the Spanish Type Culture Collection (CECT,
114 Valencia, Spain), and stored in Tryptone soy broth (TSB) (Scharlab, Barcelona, Spain) at
115 -80 °C until needed. For experimental use, the stock cultures were maintained on
116 Tryptone soy agar (TSA) (Scharlab, Barcelona, Spain) slants at 4 °C and transferred
117 monthly. Prior to each experiment, a loopful of each strain was transferred to 10 mL of
118 TSB and incubated at 37 °C for 18 h to obtain fresh early-stationary phase cells.

119 Strain of *Penicillium expansum* number 2278 was supplied by CECT (Valencia,
120 Spain). *Penicillium expansum* was grown on PDA (Potato dextrose agar, Scharlab,
121 Barcelona, Spain) in petri dishes at 28 °C for 7 days. Previous experiment, conidia were
122 collected by flooding the surface of the inoculated petri dishes with 0.05% of Tween 40

123 and peptone water scraping the mycelial surface with a spatula. 5 mL of this suspension
124 were transferred to sterile plastic tubes and shaken to obtain a homogenous suspension of
125 conidia. The conidial suspensions were diluted until to 10^6 spores/mL. The Neubauer
126 (Counting Neubauer chamber, Marienfeld, Germany) method was used to count the spore
127 concentration visualizing with a Neubauer camera in a professional biological optic
128 microscope Motic B3 Series (Barcelona, Spain).

129

130 *2.2. Extraction of active compounds from murta fruit and leaves*

131

132 Each plant material (fruit and leaves) were extracted using absolute ethanol, ethanol
133 50% and distilled water using a solvent:solid ratio of 500:1 in order to study the effect of
134 the solvent polarity on the extraction of the most relevant antioxidant compounds, and to
135 elucidate its posterior application. The extractions were carried out at 40 °C during 3 h
136 with an agitation of 150 rpm. Samples were centrifuged and the upper phases were
137 collected and used to analyze the phenolic content and the antioxidant activities. Extracts
138 obtained were named as (F-E1, F-E2, F-E3) and (L-E1, L-E2, L-E3) for extracts under
139 ethanol (E1), ethanol 50% (E2) and water (E3) of murta fruit (F) and leaves (L),
140 respectively. In the case of antimicrobial assays, extracts were concentrated until a final
141 concentration of 0.2 g sample/mL extract, and they were named with (´), F-E1´ in the case
142 of ethanolic murta fruit extract, as an example.

143

144 *2.3. Study of murta fruit and leaves extracts composition*

145

146 Hydroalcoholic murta fruit and leaves extracts were analyzed by high performance
147 liquid chromatography HPLC-PDA-FL to identify their major flavonoid compounds

148 using a Waters 2695 Separation Module equipped with a SunFire C18 Column (3.5 μm ,
149 3.0 x 150 mm) and a Waters 2996 Photodiode Array Detector, operating at 35 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a
150 flow rate of 0.5 mL/min. The injection volume was 20 μL . A nonlinear gradient of solvent
151 A (water with 0.1% formic acid) and solvent B (methanol with 0.1% formic acid) in the
152 following proportions: 0 min, 85% A, 15% B; 1 min, 85% A, 15% B; 30 min, 40 % A,
153 60 % B; 40 min, 0% A, 100% B; 45 min, 0% A, 100% B; 47 min, 85% A, 15% B; 48 min
154 85 % A, 15 % B. Quantification of antioxidant compounds were based on external
155 standard calibration methods. Integration and data elaboration were performed using
156 Empower 3 software, Build 3471. The standard solutions of catechin hydrate, rutin,
157 isoquercitrin, ellagic acid dihydrate, quercitrin hydrate and narcissin were prepared in
158 50% ethanol at a concentration range of 0,002 – 0,009 mg/mL.

159 Furthermore, due to the large composition of these extracts, a search for other
160 compounds from data of previous and recent studies were included in order to end up
161 with a more complete list of chemical compounds.

162

163 *2.4. Determination of total phenolic content*

164

165 Total phenolic content was estimated colorimetrically by means of the Folin–Ciocalteu
166 method with slight modifications (Singleton, Orthofer, & Lamuela-Raventós, 1999). A
167 volume of 100 μL of each extract was mixed with 3100 μL of distilled water and 200 μL
168 of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. The mixture was shaken and stored in the dark for 5 min.
169 Subsequently, 600 μL of an anhydrous sodium carbonate solution (20% v/v) were added
170 and stirred until homogeneous color was observed. After 2 h of reaction, the coloration
171 of the samples was recorded as their absorbance at 765 nm. Results were expressed as
172 equivalent mg gallic acid per g of dried sample.

173

174 *2.5. Antioxidant activity studies of murta extracts*

175

176 Because natural extracts are composed by several compounds with different
177 mechanisms of antioxidant action, the antioxidant power of murta fruit and leaves was
178 measured through four complementary antioxidant assays: oxygen radical absorption
179 capacity (ORAC), ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP), 2,2-diphenyl-1-
180 picrylhydrazil (DPPH) and Trolox equivalent antioxidant capacity (TEAC). ORAC
181 measures the antioxidant activity through hydrogen atom transference, FRAP is a totally
182 electron transfer based method and TEAC and DPPH measure antioxidant activity as a
183 result of both mechanisms (Deng et al., 2013; Frankel & Meyer, 2000; Prior, Wu, &
184 Schaich, 2005). All antioxidant results were expressed as mg Trolox/g fruit or leaves.

185 ORAC-FL assay was carried out following Ou et al. method (2001) with some
186 modifications (Dávalos, Bartolomé, Suberviola, & Gómez-Cordovés, 2003; Ou,
187 Hampsch-Woodill, & Prior, 2001). The reaction was carried out in 75 mM phosphate
188 buffer (pH 7.4). The mixture of extract/sample (20 mL) and fluorescein (120 mL; 70 nM
189 final concentration) was preincubated for 15 min at 37 °C. AAPH (2,2-Azobis (2-
190 methylpropionamidine) dihydrochloride) solution (60 mL; 12 mM final concentration)
191 was added rapidly using a multichannel pipette. The plate was immediately placed in the
192 reader and the fluorescence recorded every minute for 120 min (excitation wavelength
193 485 nm, emission wavelength 520 nm). A blank sample using phosphate buffer instead
194 of the antioxidant solution and eight calibration solutions using Trolox were also carried
195 out in each assay. Results were calculated based on the differences in areas under the
196 fluorescein decay curve between that of the blank and those of the samples.

197 FRAP assay is a totally electron transfer based method and measures reduction of
198 ferric 2,4,6-tripyridyl-*s*-triazine (TPTZ) to a colored product, and it was carried out in
199 accordance with Lu et al. (2011) studies (Lu et al., 2011). The FRAP reagent was prepared
200 with 2.5 mL of a TPTZ solution (10 mM) in hydrochloric acid (40 mM) and 2.5 mL of a
201 FeCl₃ solution (20 mM) mixed with 25 mL of an acetate buffer (0.3 M, pH 3.6). The
202 reaction mixture (2850 μL FRAP reagent + 150 μL extract) was stored at room
203 temperature for 30 min and the absorbance was measured at 593 nm.

204 DPPH method is based on the bleaching rate of the radical stable 2,2-diphenyl-1-
205 picrylhydrazyl monitored at a characteristic wavelength in the presence of the sample. In
206 its radical form, DPPH absorbs at 517 nm, but upon reduction by an antioxidant or a
207 radical compound its absorption decreases. TEAC assay is based on the inhibition of the
208 cationic radical 2,2-azinobis (3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonate) (ABTS^{•+}), which has a
209 characteristic long wavelength absorption maxima at 734 nm. Both radicals can be
210 neutralized either by direct reduction via electron transfers or by radical quenching via H
211 atom transfer (Prior et al., 2005). In both assays, the percentage inhibition values were
212 calculated using this equation 1:

$$213 \quad I (\%) = (A_{\text{control}} - A_{\text{sample}}) / A_{\text{control}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

214 DPPH radical-scavenging activity of murta extracts was evaluated according to the
215 method described by Okada and Okada with some modifications (Lopez de Dicastillo et
216 al., 2011; Okada & Okada, 1998). Extracts were incubated with DPPH solution for 30
217 min in the dark at room temperature, and absorbance was determined at 517 nm using a
218 spectrophotometer. ABTS radical cations were produced by reacting 7 mM ABTS in
219 water with 2.45 mM potassium persulfate (K₂S₂O₈) and then stored in darkness at room
220 temperature for 16 h. ABTS^{•+} radical solution was diluted to give absorbance value of 1
221 at 734 nm. 3 mL of ABTS^{•+} radical solution were exposed to 300 μL of murta extracts

222 and absorbance were monitored through time. All experiments were performed in
223 triplicate.

224

225 2.6. Antimicrobial activity studies

226

227 2.6.1. Determination of MIC and MBC values

228 The antimicrobial activity of murta fruit and leaf extracts against *L. monocytogenes*
229 and *E. coli*, as Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria models, respectively. Serial
230 dilutions of 0.2 g/mL concentrated extracts (E1', E2' and E3') were made up in sterile
231 buffer to study the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and the minimum
232 bactericidal concentration (MBC). The antibacterial activities of the plant extracts were
233 determined using sterile 96-well plates (Wiegand, Hilpert, & Hancock, 2008). Cell
234 cultures of each microorganism in stationary phase measured at 600 nm were diluted in
235 TSB and incubated at 37 °C until reach the exponential phase corresponding with an
236 optical density of 0.2 and a bacterial concentration of 10⁶ CFU/mL. 20 µL of these
237 solutions were added to the 200 µL final volume wells, obtaining a final concentration of
238 10⁵ CFU/mL bacteria. Wells 1-9 received the plant extract, each extract E1', E2' and E3'
239 in triplicate, and wells 10-12 served as controls (ethanol, ethanol 50% and distilled water,
240 respectively). Plant extracts were serially diluted from wells A-H to create a concentration
241 sequence. The deep-wells were incubated for 24 h at 37 °C. After the incubation period,
242 5 µL of every well was grown in a Petri dish. The lowest plant extract concentration that
243 inhibited the pathogen microorganism was reported as the MIC. The MBC was the lowest
244 concentration at which bacteria failed to grow in TSB and were not cultivable after
245 plating onto TSA (Smith-Palmer, Stewart, & Fyfe, 1998).

246

247 2.6.2. Flow Cytometry

248 The viability of *L. monocytogenes* in contact with hydroalcoholic plant extracts (F-
249 E'2 & L-E'2 for fruit and leaves extract, respectively) was studied by flow cytometry.
250 Dilutions of these extracts in peptone water were added to 10 mL of TSB in order to reach
251 a final concentration corresponding to the MIC value determined previously. Briefly, 100
252 μ L of *L. monocytogenes* in exponential phase was inoculated in each test tube and
253 incubated for 24 h at 37 °C. After the incubation period, the samples were centrifuged
254 and washed twice in sterile saline solution (0.8% NaCl). The cells were stained with the
255 cell-permeant double-stranded DNA fluorochrome SYTO-13 (Molecular Probes Europe
256 BV, Netherlands) and with propidium iodide solution (PI, Calbiochem). SYTO-13 stains
257 the nucleic acid in all cells, while PI stains the nucleic acid in cells with a damaged
258 membrane. The studies were conducted in the Central Service for Experimental Research
259 at the University of Valencia (Spain), performed with a BD FACSVerse™ (Becton
260 Dickson, USA) Flow Cytometer. Each cell was characterized by four optical parameters:
261 side scatter (SSC), forward scatter (FSC), green fluorescence for SYTO-13 (excitation
262 light 497 nm and emission light 520 nm) and red fluorescence for PI (excitation light 493
263 nm and emission light 630 nm). The software BD FACS Suite v. 1.0.3.2924 (Becton
264 Dickson, USA) was used to collect the data. An untreated control of the pathogen
265 microorganism was also analyzed.

266

267 2.6.3. Antifungal activity

268 The antifungal activity of murta extracts was studied against *Penicillium expansum*. In
269 this study, the hydroalcoholic extracts were selected due to their highest antimicrobial
270 activity. For that, 10 μ L of a conidial suspension of *Penicillium expansum* diluted until to
271 10^6 spores/mL were added in Potato Dextrose Broth (Scharlab, Barcelona, Spain) and

272 extracts were added at MBC concentrations. At the same time, tubes without
273 antimicrobial agents were used as control. Samples were incubated at 28 °C for 4 days.
274 After the incubation period, samples were centrifuged and the obtained fungal pellets
275 were weight and compared with the control. Three replicates of each sample were
276 evaluated.

277

278 *2.7. Determination of anti-tyrosinase activity*

279

280 The colorimetric tyrosinase assay was performed using the method described by
281 Momtaz et al. (2008) with minor modifications. Murta extracts with highest phenolic
282 content were analyzed. The source of tyrosinase enzyme was *Agaricus bisporus*, an edible
283 mushroom species that is native to grasslands in Europe and North America. The activity
284 of tyrosinase inhibition was determined spectrophotometrically by monitoring
285 dopachrome formation at 492 nm. The potential tyrosinase inhibitor will cause a decrease
286 in dopachrome absorption. In a 96-well plate, 70 µL of each sample solution of different
287 concentrations were combined with 30 µL of tyrosinase (333 units/mL in phosphate
288 buffer, pH 6.5) in triplicate. After incubation at 25 °C for 5 min, 110 µL of substrate
289 (2mM L-DOPA) were added to each well. Kojic acid and arbutin were used as control
290 drugs. The extracts and pure compounds were diluted in 50 mM potassium phosphate
291 buffer (pH 6.5) to appropriate concentrations. Microliter plates were incubated for 30 min
292 at 25 °C. Optical densities of the wells were then determined at 492 nm with the
293 SpectraMAX M2 Microplate Reader from Molecular Devices. The fifty percent inhibition
294 concentration (IC₅₀) value was determined by the use of SoftMax Pro Software. The
295 inhibitory effects of the test samples were expressed as the percentage of tyrosinase
296 inhibition as follows:

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = \left[\frac{(A - B) - (C - D)}{(A - B)} \right] \times 100 \quad (2)$$

297

298 where A and B denote the optical density at 492 nm of the mixture without test sample
299 (L-DOPA mixed with enzyme in buffer; the control) and without test sample and enzyme
300 (L-DOPA in buffer; the blank), respectively. C and D denote those with test sample and
301 enzyme (L-DOPA mixed with enzyme and test sample in buffer; the reaction mixture)
302 and without enzyme (L-DOPA mixed with test sample in buffer; the blank of C).

303

304 *2.7. Statistical Analysis*

305

306 One-way analyses of variance were carried out using the SPSS computer program
307 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL). Differences in pairs of mean values were evaluated by the
308 Tukey test for a confidence interval of 95%. Data were represented as the average \pm
309 standard deviation.

310

311 **3. Results and discussion**

312

313 *3.1. Composition of murta fruit and leaves extracts*

314

315 The content of some compounds in murta fruit and leaves extracts were quantified by
316 HPLC and the results are shown in the first block of Table 1, and their concentrations
317 were expressed as mg of every compound per gram of fruit or leaves. In agreement with
318 previous works, rutin, quercitrin hydrate and ellagic acid dihydrate were the principal
319 compounds identified and quantified in murta leaves (Avello et al., 2013). Other
320 flavonoids well known by their high antioxidant activity were also identified and
321 quantified, such as isoquercitrin, catechin hydrate, narcissin (isorhamnetin-3-O-

322 rutinoid) and isorhamnetin-3-O-glucoside, but their concentrations presented low
323 values. Table 1 also includes other chemical compounds identified, and sometimes
324 quantified, by previous studies. It is worthy to mention a recent work done by Peña-Cerda
325 et al., (2017) where 102 different compounds were identified from ethanolic extracts of
326 10 different genotypes of murta leaves (Peña-Cerda et al., 2017). Table 1 only presents
327 the ten compounds with highest concentration.

328 Two different extracts of murta leaves were analyzed in order to see the effect of the
329 solubility on the extraction process. Table 1 presents chemical composition of leaves
330 extractions under ethanol 50% (L-E2) and water (L-E3). Although the mixture water-
331 ethanol was able to extract higher total amount of identified components, some
332 compounds were better extracted under water, as it was the case of rutin and quercitrin
333 hydrate. Solubility is strongly affected by the nature of both the solvent and the flavonoid
334 structure (Chebil et al., 2007). The presence of sugar groups is also an important factor.
335 As it was already mentioned in the previous section, non-glycoside flavonols were better
336 extracted with ethanol, as it was the case of catechin hydrate and ellagic acid. On the other
337 hand, concentration of glycoside flavonoids were higher when extraction was carried out
338 using water (shown in Table 1 as E3).

339 In addition, the presence of these antioxidants was greatly lower in murta fruit extract.
340 Shene et al. studies have also shown the presence of flavonoids were higher in leaves than
341 fruits, and the solution 50% ethanol was the most efficient in extracting polyphenols
342 (Shene et al., 2009). Some studies have shown the presence of other compounds, such as
343 myricetin glucoside and quercetin glucosides, but these compounds were not identified
344 in this work. Shene et. coworkers found the main difference between the polyphenolic
345 profile of fruit and leaves were the presence in the leaves extracts of flavan-3-ols, both in
346 monomeric and in polymeric form (Shene et al., 2009).

347 As Table 1 shows, the total concentration of identified flavonoids in murta leaves was
348 approximately 3 times higher than the total flavonoid content of murta fruit (2.32 mg
349 antioxidants/ g fruit and 6.81 mg antioxidants/ g leaves). The same tendency presented
350 phenolic content and most antioxidant capacities shown in Figure 1.

351

352 *3.2. Phenolic content and antioxidant activity results*

353

354 Fig. 1 presents phenolic content and antioxidant activity results of murta fruit and leaf
355 extracts. Phenolic content values of murta fruit were between 23-34 mg gallic acid/g dry
356 fruit, depending the solvent used. These results were higher than the range of values
357 reported for fruits and other berries, such as plum, blackberries, raspberries and
358 strawberries (Hauser et al., 2014; Rufino et al., 2010; Wang & Lin, 2000). On the other
359 hand, murta leaves extracts presented phenolic values considerably higher than fruit
360 samples (4 times higher approximately) and higher than other leaves (Azlim Almey et al.,
361 2010; Yadav, Khare, & Singhal, 2017). Certainly, all biological properties associated to
362 murta leaves infusions are associated to these high values. It must be taken into account
363 that / Furthermore, it has also been described that flavonoids tend to combine when they
364 are part of a mixture, forming hydrogen bonds that may diminish antioxidant activity or
365 may also compete with each other at scavenging free radicals (Hidalgo, Sánchez-Moreno,
366 & Pascual-Teresa, 2010), Despite this chemical competition, as it was observed in other
367 studies, when extractive solvents were compared, highest values of antioxidant activities
368 were correlated with highest values of phenolic content (Arancibia et al., 2011; Hauser et
369 al., 2014; Peña-Cerda., et al., 2017; Rufino et al., 2010). As Fig. 1A-E show, for both fruit
370 and leaves, hydroalcoholic extracts presented highest values of phenolic content and
371 antioxidant activities due to their chemical composition. Previous works have shown

372 polyphenols in murta fruit and leaves can be divided in two major groups: (i) flavonol
373 glycosides, such as myricetin, kaempferol, and quercetin glucosides (rhamnoside,
374 dirhamnoside, xyloside and glucuronide); and (ii) non-glycoside flavanols, mainly
375 epicatechin. Glycoside flavonoids were better extracted under water, and the compounds
376 with higher hydrophobic character were better extracted with ethanol (Junqueira-
377 Gonçalves et al., 2015; Rubilar et al., 2006; Shene et al., 2009).

378 Concerning to antioxidant activity values, it is a difficult task to choose the most
379 appropriate method to determine antioxidant capacity. Therefore, it is necessary to
380 perform various methods for a better understanding of antioxidant capacities. FRAP and
381 ABTS methods are generally indicated for hydrophilic compounds. The DPPH method
382 may be employed routinely with aqueous-organic extracts containing hydrophilic and
383 lipophilic compounds. As Fig. 1 shows, results obtained from different methods are not
384 always correlated, mainly when these methods are based on a single mechanism of action,
385 as it was the case of results obtained following ORAC (Fig. 1B) and FRAP (Fig. 1C)
386 assays, which are methods based on proton and electron transference, respectively.
387 Differences in the measurement of antioxidant activity through different assays have
388 already been reported (Dudonne, Vitrac, Coutiere, Woillez, & Merillon, 2009; Zhu, Lian,
389 Guo, Peng, & Zhou, 2011). Interestingly, when results of antioxidants activities measured
390 through FRAP and ORAC assays were compared, fruit extracts presented highest values
391 when activities were measured through FRAP (approximately 70 mg Trolox per gram of
392 fruit), while leaves extracts presented highest antioxidant capacities through ORAC
393 method (approximately 274 mg Trolox per gram of leaves). These results only indicated
394 that compounds of fruit and leaves extracts presented different mechanism of antioxidant
395 action. Chemical compounds from leaves extracts presented preference to transfer proton
396 as antioxidant mechanism. Nevertheless, when total antioxidant activity was measured by

397 DPPH (Fig. 1E) and TEAC (Fig. 1D) methods, which were able to measure the
398 antioxidant ability by single electron transfer and proton donor mechanisms, both
399 methods presented the same tendency than polyphenolic content results.

400

401 3.3. Antimicrobial activity results

402

403 3.3.1. MIC and MBC determination results

404 The evaluation of antibacterial activities of murta fruit and leaf extracts against *E. coli*
405 and *L. monocytogenes* were quantitatively assessed by determining MIC and MBC
406 values. Murta fruit and leaves extracts exhibited all antimicrobial activity against both
407 bacteria. As Table 2 shows, results depended on three factors: i) type of extraction solvent
408 (water and ethanol); ii) type of sample (fruit and leaves); and iii) type of microorganisms
409 (Gram-positive or negative).

410 Extracts with highest composition of antimicrobial active agents content would present
411 lowest MIC and MBC values. In general, there was a correlation between phenolic
412 content values of different extracts and antimicrobial activities. Hydroalcoholic extracts
413 showed highest antimicrobial activities conducting to the lowest MIC values, excepting
414 the case of the ethanolic murta fruit extract (F-E1') which presented the highest
415 antibacterial ability against *E. coli*. Fig. 1 already showed ethanolic and hydroethanolic
416 fruit extracts reported similar phenolic content, but probably, some compounds better
417 extracted under ethanol were more effective against Gram-negative. Hauser and
418 coauthors (2014) have studied the antimicrobial activity of murta leaf extracts against *L.*
419 *innocua*, and the highest antimicrobial activity was also obtained with hydroalcoholic
420 extracts. The count reduction was 3.5 log-cycles for the aqueous and 4.5 log cycles for
421 the 50% ethanolic extract (Hauser et al., 2014).

422 In addition, as expected from Table 1 data and phenolic content values, antimicrobial
423 capacities of fruit extracts were slightly lower than values obtained with leaf extracts due
424 to the different chemical composition of fruit and leaves. Other studies have also shown
425 that leaves presented higher level of polyphenols, such as flavan-3-ols and flavonol
426 glycosides, and other active agents extracted that could have antimicrobial activity, such
427 as organic acids and small lignin fragments (Shene et al., 2009). Surprisingly, fruit
428 extracts were more effective against Gram negative bacteria, such as *E. coli*, than leaves
429 extracts. This fact was probably due to the presence of some anthocyanins on murta fruit
430 extracts, as shown in other studies (Junqueira et al., 2015). Antibacterial activity of berries
431 and other anthocyanin-containing fruits can be caused by multiple mechanism and
432 synergism between various compounds including anthocyanins, weak organic acids,
433 phenolic acids and their complex chemical mixtures (Cisowska, Wojnicz, & Hendrich,
434 2011).

435 As Table 2 shows, and in agreement with previous studies, extracts presented highest
436 antimicrobial activities against *L. monocytogenes*, a Gram-positive bacteria. Gram-
437 negative organism have a major defense system and are less susceptible to the action of
438 many antimicrobial compounds because the presence of an outer membrane surrounding
439 the cell wall that limit the diffusion of hydrophobic substances through its
440 lipopolysaccharide covering (Vaara, 1992). Conversely, Gram-positive bacteria only
441 have a peptidoglycan without external membrane, being the path for the antimicrobial
442 components action is more accessible (Gutierrez, Rodriguez, Barry-Ryan, & Bourke,
443 2008; Harvey, Champe, & Fisher, 2007). Antimicrobial substances interact with
444 microbial membrane proteins, enzymes and lipids, thereby altering cell permeability and
445 permitting the loss of protons, ions and macromolecules. The mechanism of antibacterial
446 action can be divided in two important aspects: i) inhibition on the synthesis of bacterial

447 nucleic acids; ii) cellular membrane damage causing change on fluidity and exit of
448 intracellular compounds. Other studies have also shown that the presence of bioactive
449 compounds from berries hindered the adherence of bacteria to epithelial cells, which is
450 necessary for colonization, and infection of many pathogens (Gensokowsky et al., 2015).
451 Anthocyanins of cranberry concentrate have also produced a down-regulation of genes
452 encoding outer membrane proteins in *E. coli* O157:H7 (Wu et al., 2013).

453

454 3.3.2. Cytometry results

455 Flow cytometry assays were carried out to study the viability of cells exposed to murta
456 extracts. Tests were performed with *Listeria monocytogenes*, since this microorganism
457 showed higher sensitivity to murta extracts (shown in Table 2). SYTO-13 is a
458 fluorochrome able to penetrate all bacterial membranes and bind nucleic acid of the cells.
459 On the other hand, PI penetrates the cell membranes when they are damaged (Rodriguez,
460 Seguer, Rocabayera, & Manresa, 2004). As Fig. 2 shows, the samples were successfully
461 stained. The assay demonstrated that the percentage of damaged cells after treatment with
462 MIC values of hydroalcoholic murta extracts was in accordance with the antimicrobial
463 effect observed in the previous studies.

464 As it can be observed in Fig. 2A, the positive control of *L. monocytogenes* control
465 presented 77.41% of alive cells (stained with SYTO-13) and 21.17% dead bacteria
466 (stained with PI). This value of non viable cells can be explained by the different phases
467 of cellular cycle during the cytometry assay.

468 The damaged of *L. monocytogenes* was evident after treatment with murta extracts.
469 The effect of hydroalcoholic murta fruit extract produced a dead population of 93.21%,
470 as it can be seen in Fig. 2B. After the interaction between the bacteria and the
471 hydroalcoholic murta leaves extract at MIC concentration, the result was found to be

472 97.93% of non-viable cells (Fig. 2C). In this sample, the evaluation of the cytometry assay
473 was very difficult since leaves extract was composed by some components which
474 coloration affected the analysis by the Flow Cytometer. The fact that emission and
475 excitation light of some leaf-extract compounds (probably chlorophylls) were similar to
476 those of the fluorochromes affected the analysis, and the graph obtained was not so clear
477 as with the other samples.

478

479 3.3.3. Antifungal activity results

480 Antimicrobial activity of murta extracts against *Penicillium expansum* was studied in
481 liquid medium. Hydroalcoholic extracts of fruit and leaf produced an inhibition growth
482 of $(3.79 \pm 0.22)\%$ and $(4.76 \pm 0.30)\%$, respectively. Although antifungal activity was
483 higher with the leaf extracts, both hydroalcoholic extracts showed low antifungal activity
484 against *Penicillium expansum*. Low antifungal effectiveness of murta fruit and leaf
485 extracts against *Aspergillus niger* and *Penicillium expansum* was already observed by
486 other authors. Climatic conditions during plant cultivation, the different areas of
487 cultivation and the genotype are determining factors in the phenolic profile of murta
488 leaves and fruits. Extreme climatic conditions could increase the phenolic profile of
489 leaves. The influence of all these factors makes it difficult to compare studies between
490 different authors. In addition, it is important to highlight the concentration of these
491 extracts that implied their higher effectiveness against microorganism growth (Alfaro et
492 al., 2013; Ferrer-Gallego, Hernández-Hierro, Rivas-Gonzalo, & Escribano-Bailon, 2012;
493 Shene et al., 2009).

494

495 3.4. Anti-tyrosinase activity results

496

497 Fig. 3 shows the results of tyrosinase inhibitory activities by the hydroethanolic
498 extracts of murta fruit and leaves, expressed as the concentration necessary to inhibit
499 tyrosinase activity at 50% (CE₅₀). Anti-tyrosinase activities of aqueous extracts were also
500 measured in order to confirm the same tendency observed in other activities. Results
501 confirmed hydroalcoholic extracts of both murta fruit and leaves presented the highest
502 anti-tyrosinase activities, resulting on CE₅₀ values approximately 2 to 3 times lower than
503 results obtained from aqueous extracts. It was also clear that murta leaves presented
504 higher tyrosinase inhibitory effect than fruit samples. As it was expected, results followed
505 similar relationship with phenolic content of the extracts. Such as the work done by Sun
506 et al. (2017) in which the anti-tyrosinase activities and concentrations of bound phenolic
507 extracts (BPE) of rape bee pollen exhibited linear correlation. Free phenolic extracts
508 (FPE) of rape bee pollen showed higher activity than BPE. Inhibitory activity against
509 tyrosinase was also observed for some phenolic compounds, such as quercetin, benzoic
510 acid and their derivatives. Therefore, inhibitory tyrosinase activity of FPE and BPE is
511 related to their phenolic profiles. For its part, Kaewnarin et al., (2016) moderate
512 correlation was observed between tyrosinase inhibitory activity of all mushroom species
513 and their phenolic ($r = 0.420$) and flavonoid ($r = 0.557$) contents. According to their
514 phenolic profiles, high levels of flavonoid compounds were found, such as catechin, rutin,
515 apigenin and rosmarinic acid. Chang (2009) demonstrated that flavonoid compounds
516 have potential as natural tyrosinase inhibitors. Additionally, rosmarinic acid displayed a
517 strong tyrosinase inhibitory activity on mouse melanoma cell line B16F10 at low
518 concentration (Oliveira, Palu, Weffort-Santos, & Oliveira, 2013). Generally, the number
519 of hydroxyl groups of the phenolic compounds could influence the tyrosinase inhibitory
520 activity that forms a hydrogen bond to the active site of low enzyme leading to the low
521 enzyme activity (Alam, Yoo, & Lee, 2011). Therefore, the presence of compounds with

522 antioxidant activity may be one of the important mechanisms involved in tyrosinase
523 inhibition (Kaewnarin, Suwannarach, Kumala, & Lumyong, 2016). In addition, several
524 researchers have reported the anti-tyrosinase of various phenolic resources, including
525 soybean, *Ornithogalum narbonense*, mentha and wild edible mushroom (Fatiha et al.,
526 2015; Kaewnarin et al., 2016; Shukla et al., 2016; Zengin, Uysal, Ceylan, & Aktumsek,
527 2015).

528 The variation in activity between fruit and leaves and solvent extraction might be
529 explained based on the chemical composition of extracts and the potential synergistic
530 effect of individual extract components. Tyrosinase inhibitors repress conversion of
531 tyrosinase to DOPA, and subsequently melanin. Thus, tyrosinase inhibitory activity might
532 be dependent on the hydroxyl groups of phenolic compounds, which forms hydrogen
533 bonds with enzyme sites to promote steric hindrance, conformational changes, and
534 suppression of enzymatic activity. Other studies have also shown interesting results of
535 anti-tyrosinase activities of phenolic compounds from natural sources, such as green tea
536 and grape seed (Momtaz et al., 2008; Yamakoshi et al., 2006).

537 The values obtained for control drugs were CE_{50} (arbutin) > 100 g/L and CE_{50} (Kojic
538 acid) = 35.62 mg/L. As it was already shown in other studies, natural extracts presented
539 pretty low inhibitory activities when compared to kojic acid, but if the comparison is done
540 with arbutin, results were quite interesting, mainly in the case of aqueous leaves extracts
541 (Momtaz et al., 2008).

542

543 **4. Conclusion**

544

545 Because evaluation methods of antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-tyrosinase
546 activities have not been sufficiently standardized yet, making comparisons with other

547 studies and fruits is difficult. Even though, the data obtained add valuable information to
548 current knowledge on the nutritional properties of murta fruit and leaves, such as an
549 interesting phenolic content, considerable antioxidant and antimicrobial capacities and a
550 promising effect as tyrosinase inhibitor. HPLC confirmed the presence of phenolic acids
551 and flavonoids, and quantification revealed highest concentration in the case of murta
552 leaves extract. Hydroalcoholic extracts of murta leaves were the most promising for the
553 cosmetic industry showing highest anti-tyrosinase activities. Traditional uses of murta
554 fruit and leaves were validated through phenolic content results and antioxidant assays.

555 New applications of the murta fruit and leaves, naturally occurring or as extract, on
556 functional food, nutraceutical and cosmetic products may be interesting thanks to their
557 antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-tyrosinase capabilities.

558

559

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565

566

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743

744 **Table 1**

745 Chemical composition of some quantified flavonoids of murta fruit and leaves extracts,
 746 expressed as mg of compound per gram of fruit/leaves.

Rt (min)	Compound	F - E2	L- E2	L- E3
9,02	Catechin hydrate	ND	0.57	ND
22,10	Rutin (Quercetin-3-O-rutinoside)	1.30	1.99	2.42
22,35	Isoquercitrin (Quercetin-3-O-glucoside)	0.20	0.63	0.60
23,16	Ellagic acid dihydrate	0.15	2.56	0.80
24,96	Quercitrin hydrate (Quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside)	ND	0.81	1.14
25,37	Narcissin (Isorhamnetin-3-O-rutinoside) + Isorhamnetin-3-O-glucoside	0.67*	0.25*	0.17*
	*quantified with narcissin as standard			
TOTAL COMPOUNDS (mg antioxidants/g sample)		2.32	6.81	5.13

747 Rt: retention time; ND: not detected

748

749 **Table 2**

750 MIC and MBC values expressed in (mg/mL) of murta fruit and leaf extracts.

Extract	<i>Escherichia coli</i>		<i>Listeria monocytogenes</i>	
	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC
F-E1´	1.2	1.7	0.6	0.9
F-E2´	3.8	5	0.2	0.5
F-E3´	8.3	10.0	1.8	2.2
L-E1´	5	6.7	0.2	0.5
L-E2´	4.1	5.5	0.07	0.09
L-E3´	10.3	12.0	0.7	0.9

751

752

753 **Figure captions**

754

755 **Fig. 1.** Phenolic content and antioxidant activity results of murta fruit (F-E1, F-E2, F-E3)
756 and leaf extracts (L-E1, L-E2, L-E3) obtained through different methods: A) Folin
757 Ciocalteu, B) ORAC, C) FRAP, D) TEAC, and E) DPPH assays. Letters a-d indicate
758 significant differences among the extracts of the same method.

759

760 **Fig.2.** Dual parameter SYTO-13/PI fluorescence histograms obtained by staining *L.*
761 *monocytogenes*: A) Control samples; B) treated with hydroalcoholic murta fruit extract
762 at MIC; C) treated with hydroalcoholic murta leaf extract at MIC.

763

764 **Fig. 3.** Concentration necessary of hydroalcoholic and aqueous extracts of murta fruit and
765 leaves to inhibit tyrosinase activity at 50%. Letters a-d indicate significant differences
766 among values.

767

770 **Fig.2.**

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773

774 **Fig. 3.**

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- 776 - Buscar referencias de catacterizacion antocianinas murta fruit (Reviewer 1)
- 777 - Revisar como se secaron las muestras
- 778 - Buscar ref con valores polifenolicos
- 779 - Abstract- incluir numerical values
- 780

Compounds	Murta fruit			Murta leaves			References
	ethanol 50%	ethanol 85%	water	ethanol	ethanol 50%	water	
Catechin hydrate	ND		2.696		0.57	ND	Jofre et al., 2016; Shene et al., 2012
Rutin (Quercetin-3-O-rutinoside)	1.30	X		X	1.99	2.42	Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015; Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2009
Isoquercitrin (Quercetin-3-O-glucoside)	0.20	X		X	0.63	0.60	Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015; Peña-Cerda et al., 2017
Ellagic acid dihydrate	0.15			X	2.56	0.80	Peña-Cerda et al., 2017
Quercitrin hydrate (Quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside)	ND	X			0.81	1.14	Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015
Narcissin (Isorhamnetin-3-O-rutinoside) + Isorhamnetin-3-O-glucoside	0.67				0.25	0.17	
Cafeico ácido-3-glucósido		X		X			Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015; Peña-Cerda et al., 2017
Quercetin		X	0.009	X	X		Jofre et al., 2016; Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015; Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012
Gallic acid		X	0.059	X			Jofre et al., 2016; Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015; Peña-Cerda et al., 2017
Luteolina		X					Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015
Kaempferol		X	0.014				Jofre et al., 2016; Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015
Kaempferol-3-glucósido		X		X			Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012
Luteolina-3-glucósido		X					Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015
p ácido -cumárico		X					Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015
Myricetin		X	0.115	X	X		Jofre et al., 2016; Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015; Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012
Quercetin-3-β-D-glucoside			0.141				Jofre et al., 2016; Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015
Myricetin glucoside	X			X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012, 2009
Quercetin dirhamnoside	X			X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2009
Quercetin glucoside	X				X		Shene et al., 2012, 2009
Quercetin glucuronide	X			X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012, 2009
Flavan-3-ol (E)GC					X		Shene et al., 2009
Flavan-3-ol (E)C					X		Shene et al., 2009
Polymeric flavan-3-ol (E)C					X		Shene et al., 2009
Myricetin xyloside				X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012, 2009
Myricetin rhamnoside				X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2009
Quercetin rhamnoside				X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012
Galloyl-quercetin hexoside				X			Peña-Cerda et al., 2017
Quercetin conjugate					X		Shene et al., 2012
Myricetin conjugate					X		Shene et al., 2012
Myricetin rhamnosyl glucoside				X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012

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Luteolina		X					Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015
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Luteolina-3-glucósido		X					Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015
p ácido -cumárico		X					Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015
Myricetin		X	0.115	X	X		Jofre et al., 2016; Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015; Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012
Quercetin-3-β-D-glucoside			0.141				Jofre et al., 2016; Junqueira-Gonçalves et al., 2015
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Quercetin glucoside	X				X		Shene et al., 2012, 2009
Quercetin glucuronide	X			X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012, 2009
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Flavan-3-ol (E)C					X		Shene et al., 2009
Polymeric flavan-3-ol (E)C					X		Shene et al., 2009
Myricetin xyloside				X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012, 2009
Myricetin rhamnoside				X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2009
Quercetin rhamnoside				X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012
Galloyl-quercetin hexoside				X			Peña-Cerda et al., 2017
Quercetin conjugate					X		Shene et al., 2012
Myricetin conjugate					X		Shene et al., 2012
Myricetin rhamnosyl glucoside				X	X		Peña-Cerda et al., 2017; Shene et al., 2012

Compounds	Murta fruit			Murta leaves			References
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Rutin (Quercetin-3-O-rutinoside)	1.30	X		X	1.99	2.42	b, c, d
Isoquercitrin (Quercetin-3-O-glucoside)	0.20	X		X	0.63	0.60	b, c
Ellagic acid dihydrate	0.15			X	2.56	0.80	c
Quercitrin hydrate (Quercetin-3-O-rhamnoside)	ND	X			0.81	1.14	b
Narcissin (Isorhamnetin-3-O-rutinoside) + Isorhamnetin-3-O-glucoside	0.67				0.25	0.17	
Cafeico ácido-3-glucósido		X		X			b,c
Quercetin		X	0.009	X	X		a, b, c, e
Gallic acid		X	0.059	X			a, b, c, e
Luteolina		X					b
Kaempferol		X	0.014				a,b
Kaempferol-3-glucósido		X		X			b, c, e
Luteolina-3-glucósido		X					b
p ácido -cumárico		X					b
Myricetin		X	0.115	X	X		a, b, c, e
Quercetin-3-β-D-glucoside			0.141				a, b, c, e
Myricetin glucoside	X			X	X		c, d, e
Quercetin dirhamnoside	X			X	X		c, d, e
Quercetin glucoside	X				X		c, d
Quercetin glucuronide	X			X	X		c, d, e
Flavan-3-ol (E)GC					X		d
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Polymeric flavan-3-ol (E)C					X		d
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Myricetin rhamnoside				X	X		c, d
Quercetin rhamnoside				X	X		c, e
Galloyl-quercetin hexoside				X			c
Quercetin conjugate					X		e
Myricetin conjugate					X		e
Myricetin rhamnosyl glucoside				X	X		c, e

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